

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

	$\mu_{\text{eff}}^{\#}$	Electronic spectral peaks*					
		Ligand Field Parameters					
Co(4-pic) ₂ Cl Cl	4.66	Observed		Calculated			
		${}^4T_1(F)$	${}^4T_1(P)$	ν_1	D_q	B'	λ'
Co(4-pic) ₂ Cl Cl	4.66	21.05, 19.9, 19.42 sh, 17.36(510), 16.00(930), 15.75(780), 15.15 sh, 8.00(45), 6.72(65), 6.25(39).					
Co(4-pic) ₂ I I	4.52	22.1, 21.0, 19.60, 17.2(530), 16.08 sh, 15.25(640), 12.0(585), 8.7(35), 7.10(70), 6.0(75), 5.8(40).					
Co(4-pic) ₂ Cl Cl		6.72	16.00	3.88	0.388	0.68	-0.186
Co(4-pic) ₂ I I		6.01	15.25	3.50	0.350	0.73	-0.142

[#] In B.M., $T = 293 \pm 3^\circ$.

* The peak positions are in kK ($1\text{K} = 1\text{ cm}^{-1}$); the values in parentheses are molar absorptivity.

three bands around 6.5 kK are taken as components of ν_a transitions of a complex of C_{2v} symmetry. Thus the electronic spectra of these complexes indicate distortion from tetrahedral symmetry. The ligand field parameters have been calculated for these complexes. The mean crystal field strength follow the sequence $I < Cl$.

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Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) Complexes of N-4-Methyl-7-Hydroxy-8-Acetocoumarinylidene-*o*-Aminophenol

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COMPLEXES of the composition $H[M(C_{15}H_{13}NO_4)_2]$ [$M = Cr^{3+}$, Mn^{3+} or Fe^{3+}] with N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene-*o*-aminophenol (H_2 MHACAP) have been prepared and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity, electronic, infrared, pmr and magnetic measurements. Infrared spectral study reveals the tridentate (ONO) nature of the ligand. Electronic spectral data and magnetic moments of the complexes show octahedral geometry.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Nitrates of chromium(III) and iron(III) were used. Manganese(III) acetate dihydrate was prepared by the known method¹. 4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl coumarin was prepared² and the ligand (Schiff base), H_2 MHACAP (m.p. 161°) was prepared as reported earlier^{3,4}.

For the preparation of the complexes, a slight excess of hot ethanolic solution of the ligand was added to an ethanolic solution of a metal salt dropwise with constant stirring. Sodium acetate (2 g) was added to the reaction mixture and refluxed for 30 min. The resulting mixture was concentrated to half of its original volume and the solid obtained was filtered, washed well with hot water followed by a little hot ethanol. The product was dried in air. Mn(III) complex was prepared as above without the use of sodium acetate.

Elemental analysis (Table 1), carried out by standard methods, were consistent with the formulations of the compounds. The molar conductances for $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene medium range between 105-128 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mole}^{-1}$ indicating the uni-unielectrolytic nature of the compounds.

The magnetic measurements were made on a Guoy balance at room temp using $Hg[CO(SCN)_4]$ as calibrant. The electronic spectra of all the complexes were recorded in DMF on a Cary-14 recording spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} on a Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. PMR spectra in $CDCl_3$ were recorded on Varian T-60 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

The present Cr(III) complex exhibits the magnetic moments 3.73 B.M. which is close to spin only value for octahedral geometry^{5,6}. The spectra of Cr(III) complex exhibits bands at 11800 and 18170 and a shoulder at 23540. The ν_o band at 18170 and the shoulder at 23540 may be assigned to

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour (decomp ; °C)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		C	H	N	M	
H[Cr(MHACAP) ₃]	Grey (177-179)	64.50 (64.76)	3.91 (4.04)	4.07 (4.19)	7.65 (7.79)	3.73
H[Mn(MHACAP) ₃]	Reddish black (184-186)	64.37 (64.47)	3.90 (4.02)	4.00 (4.17)	8.05 (8.20)	4.97
H[Fe(MHACAP) ₃]	Pinkish red (189-191)	64.21 (64.38)	3.96 (4.02)	3.98 (4.17)	8.14 (8.32)	3.37

$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_4 = \text{MHACAP}$

${}^4\text{T}_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ (ν_1) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \leftarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively for octahedral complex⁷.

The magnetic moment value of the present Mn(III) complex (4.97 B.M.) indicate the presence of four unpaired electrons corresponding to high spin manganese(III) state with ${}^5\text{E}_g$ ground term. The electronic spectra of the complex show three bands at ~ 13500 , ~ 22900 and ~ 25000 cm^{-1} . Only one spin allowed transition ${}^5\text{E}_g \rightarrow {}^5\text{T}_{2g}$ is expected for weak field octahedral manganese(III) complex^{8,9}. The presence of three band in the complex indicates lowering of the O_h symmetry due to Jahn-Teller distortion.

The magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of the present Fe(III) complex at room temp is 3.37 B.M. The electronic absorption spectra of Fe(III) complex exhibits bands at 15885, 17550, 20000 assignable to the ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \leftarrow {}^6\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^4\text{T}_{2g} \leftarrow {}^6\text{A}_{1g}$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{1g} \leftarrow {}^6\text{A}_{1g}$ transition, respectively in the octahedral stereochemistry¹⁰.

IR and PMR spectral studies :

A strong band around 3500 cm^{-1} occurs in the ir spectra of the ligand which is assigned to the νOH^{11} . This νOH band is absent in the spectra of the complexes suggesting that the OH group of the ligand participates in complex formation. The high intensity band around 1700 cm^{-1} in the ligand can be assigned to the $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ mode. This band is observed at almost the same position in the complexes ruling out the involvement of carbonyl group of the ligand in complexation. A considerable fall in the intensity and frequency in $-(\text{CH}_3)-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ band (ligand ~ 1625 cm^{-1} and complexes ~ 1550 cm^{-1}) indicate the M-N bonding^{12,13}. The band in the region $425-475$ cm^{-1} and $500-550$ cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu\text{M}-\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$, respectively^{14,15}.

The mode of bonding discussed above gets further support from the pmr spectral data (chemical shift in δ values down field from TMS internal reference) of the ligand and its corresponding 1 : 2 metal complexes.

The azomethine methyl protons $[-(\text{CH}_3)-\text{C}=\text{N}-]$ appear at 2.9 in the ligand and at 3.14, 3.13 and 3.16, respectively in their metal complexes showing down field shift and this may be due to the deshielding caused by coordination through the azomethine group to metals. The peak at 9.40 due to phenolic proton of the ligand disappears in the com-

plexes indicating chelating nature of the ligand. A number of signals between 7.0 to 7.85 appear due to aromatic protons and a singlet at 1.96 due to a methyl group in the compounds.

Based on the above observations following structure can be proposed for the complexes.

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